

Synthesis, Characterisation and Thermal Properties of Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes of Salicylaldehyde Schiff Bases

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Coordination ability of different Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and their analytical applications have been studied extensively¹. In continuation of our earlier work on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases, we report here the results of spectroscopic and thermal investigations of some dioxouranium(VI) complexes of four Schiff base ligands.

Results and Discussion

Dioxouranium complexes of 2-hydroxynaphthalidene-*o*-aminopyridine is coloured brown while all the others are orange-red. The very low values of molar conductance of the complexes (0.56–0.85 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in nitrobenzene indicate that the complexes are nonelectrolytes, and the elemental analysis data (Table 1) show that the complexes have the general formula UO_2L_2 . The complexes are diamagnetic. Electronic spectra of uranium complexes were measured in nitrobenzene. All the ligands contain three characteristic bands at $\approx 33\,000$, $38\,400$ and $48\,700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be due to their $\eta \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\eta \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions. These bands slightly red-shifted in complexes. Besides, two more bands were seen in the complexes at $23\,200$ and $21\,700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be attributed to its very strong charge transfer bands from ligand to metal.

The ir spectra of the ligands showed broad band at $2\,500$ – $3\,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (H-bonded hydroxyl group) which was absent in the complexes suggesting deprotonation of OH group and coordination of the phenolic oxygen atom. The bands at $1\,600$ – $1\,620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N) in Schiff base appreciably shifted to higher frequency region in the complexes at $1\,650$ – $1\,640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordinations with uranyl ion².

In the dioxouranium(VI) complexes, the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band occurring at $1\,300$ – $1\,340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is about 30 cm^{-1} higher than the corresponding $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band in the ligand, which indicates the CO^- coordinates to the metal. All the complexes are characterised with a band at 900 – 920 cm^{-1} which is a clear evidence of O=U=O band³. Medium bands found at 500 – 550 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations respectively⁴.

The mode of bonding discussed above is further supported by the ¹H nmr spectral studies. The signals observed at 15.8 (L'H), 13.4 (L''H), 15 (L'''H) and 15.4 ppm (L''''H) are due to hydrogen bonded OH protons which disappeared in the spectra of the corresponding uranium complexes and this shows the deprotonation of the functional groups and the coordination of oxygen to the central metal atom. The proton signals for the azomethine protons at 9.4 (L'H), 9.4 (L''H), 9.2 (L'''H) and 9.9 ppm (L''''H) in the ligands shifted downfield in the spectra of the complexes and thus indicating deshielding. This is probably on account of the donation of the lone-pair of electrons by the nitrogen to the central metal atom due to the formation of a coordinate linkage⁵. Based on the above data, an octahedral structure may be suggested for these six coordinated uranium complexes.

The instrumental TG curves were redrawn as mass vs temperature (TG) and also as the rate of mass loss vs temperature (DTG). Independent pyrolytic decomposition was carried out in each sample for checking the mass-loss obtained by TG experiments. The order of reaction, activation energy, frequency factor and entropy of activation of the system were calculated using Coats-Redfern⁶ and Horowitz-Metzger⁷ equations and data are summarised in Table 2. All the TG curves show single well-defined one stage process in which the decomposition of the ligand has taken place. According to the results (Table 2) obtained from the TG curves, all the above decomposition reactions have an order $n = 1$. All the complexes have negative entropy which indicates that activated complexes have more ordered system than the reactants and that the reactions are slower. The entropies of activation of chelates are also comparable. The initial decomposition temperature is frequently used to define the relative thermal stability of metal chelates⁸. Based on the experimental results, the relative thermal stability of various chelates can be given as $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}'_2] < [\text{UO}_2\text{L}''_2] \approx [\text{UO}_2\text{L}'''_2] < [\text{UO}_2\text{L}''''_2]$.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Metal %	C	H	N	S	Br
$[\text{UO}_2\text{L}'_2]$ (Orange red)	36.41 (35.84)	42.91 43.54	3.34 2.43	8.93 8.46)	—	—
$[\text{UO}_2\text{L}''_2]$ (Orange red)	27.78 (29.02)	34.87 35.15	2.03 1.72	6.42 6.83	—	18.43 19.48)
$[\text{UO}_2\text{L}'''_2]$ (Orange red)	34.46 (35.20)	35.18 35.64	2.78 1.79	7.91 8.31	8.87 9.51)	—
$[\text{UO}_2\text{L}''''_2]$ (Brown)	31.56 (31.28)	51.12 50.44	2.38 2.64	6.85 7.35)	—	—

L'H = Salicylidene-*o*-aminopyridine, L''H = 5-bromosalicylidene-*o*-aminopyridine, L'''H = salicylidene-*o*-aminothiazole, L''''H = 2-hydroxynaphthalidene-*o*-aminopyridine.

TABLE 2—KINETIC DATA FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Peak temp. K	%Mass-loss		Coats-Redfern equation			Horowitz-Metzger equation		
		TG	Theoretical	E^* kcal mol ⁻¹	Z	ΔS^* e.u.	E^* kcal mol ⁻¹	Z	ΔS^* e.u.
[UO ₂ L ₂]	683	57.50	57.73	49.23	1.56 10 ¹³	0.177	48.46	2.78 10 ¹³	1.32
[UO ₂ L ₂ ']	723	65.25	65.77	42.90	6.50 10 ¹⁰	-10.82	43.05	7.12 10 ¹³	-10.63
[UO ₂ L ₂ ']	643	58.67	58.50	23.29	2.12 10 ⁵	-35.69	25.54	2.48 10 ⁶	-30.81
[UO ₂ L ₂ ']	683	62.78	63.20	37.44	2.68 10 ⁹	-17.05	38.42	1.80 10 ¹¹	-13.20

Experimental

The ligands (L'H, L''H, L'''H and L''''H) were prepared by the condensation of the corresponding aldehyde and amine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in distilled methanol. Dioxouranium(VI) complexes were prepared by refluxing methanolic solution of uranyl nitrate hexahydrate with the above ligands in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 2 h. Metal chelates which separated on cooling were filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The molar conductance of the complexes were measured in nitrobenzene/methanol. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-d₆) on a Hitachi R-600 FT-NMR spectrophotometer. Thermograms were taken using a Perkin-Elmer 7 series thermobalance (heating rate 10° min⁻¹).

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